

The Constitution of Rottlerin from Indian Kamala.

Part II.

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In a previous paper by one of the present authors (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 2044), rottlerin—the colouring matter of Indian *Kamala*, or *Rori* as it is commonly called in the United Provinces, was isolated and its constitution investigated to a considerable extent by studying the degradation products of the substance and its derivatives under the influence of various chemical reagents. From the results of that investigation it was concluded that rottlerin must have the molecular formula $C_{33}H_{30}O_6$, and that it must contain four benzene nuclei, of which (1) two must be phloroglucinol residues, (2) one must be in the residue $C_6H_5 \cdot CH : CH \cdot C$, and (3) one must be a benzene nucleus containing at least three side-chains. The present investigation was therefore undertaken to elucidate further the constitution of the substance.

The method of attack at the problem, undertaken in the present investigation, was by nitration and bromination of acetyl-, and of methoxy-rottlerin, and subsequent degradation of the nitro-, and bromo-, acetyl-, and methoxy-rottlerin thus formed, by oxidation with neutral potassium permanganate. In almost every case a 2:4-disubstituted benzoic acid was isolated together with some 3:6-disubstituted phthalic and 2:5-disubstituted terephthalic acids. The identification of the latter acids was a matter of considerable difficulty, but was finally overcome by heating with soda-lime, when *para*-disubstituted benzenes were obtained. Thus hepta-acetyl-rottlerin on nitration with fuming nitric acid gave a hexa-nitro-compound, which by oxidation with neutral potassium permanganate gave 2:4-dinitro-benzoic acid together with 3:6-dinitro-phthalic acid and 2:5-dinitro-terephthalic acid. The identification of the latter acids was carried out by heating with soda-lime when *p*-dinitro-benzene was obtained in each case. Hepta-acetyl-rottlerin on bromination with excess of bromine in acetic acid solution under pressure gave a hexa-bromo-hepta-acetyl-rottlerin, which on oxida-

tion with permanganate gave 2:4-dibromo-benzoic acid and a mixture of phthalic and terephthalic acids. Hexa-methoxy-rottlerin on nitration with fuming nitric acid gave a hexanitro compound which on similar oxidation with permanganate gave a mixture of 2:4-dinitro-benzoic acid, 3:6-dinitro-phthalic and 2:5-dinitro-terephthalic acids. In none of the above cases of degradation however could any derivative of phloroglucinol be isolated.

From the experimental results of this paper and those of the previous communication, it seems fairly conclusive that rottlerin has probably the following constitution:—

The positions indicated by asterisks are probably the positions taken up by nitro groups in nitro-acetyl and nitro-methoxy-rottlerin. The structure of rottlerin suggested above is of course provisional subject to further investigation and revision.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Hexanitro-hepta-acetyl-rottlerin, $C_{23}H_{17}O_9(NO_2)_6(C_6H_5O)_2$.—Hepta-acetyl-rottlerin (10 g.) was gradually added to fuming nitric acid (50 c.c., d 1.52 in the cold. The acetyl-derivative very rapidly dissolved in the acid, and when the addition was complete, the solution was warmed on the water-bath for about half an hour. On pouring into water the hexa-nitro compound separated in yellow flocks which were filtered off, washed with water and finally crystallised from dilute alcohol.

It is a yellow crystalline substance which is fairly soluble in most of the organic solvents but insoluble in water. On heating it does not melt, but gradually darkens in colour and finally decomposes with evolution of gas. When suddenly heated to a high

temperature it decomposes with a mild explosion. Found: N, 7.1. $C_{13}H_{11}O_6(NO_2)_6(C_6H_5O)_7$, requires N, 7.4 per cent.).

Hexanitro-rottlerin, $C_{13}H_{11}O_6(NO_2)_6$.—The above nitro-acetyl derivative (5 g.) was heated on the water-bath with a 3% solution of sodium hydroxide (200 c.c.) for about an hour, when the compound completely dissolved and the solution was of a dark red colour. On acidifying with dilute hydrochloric acid the hexa-nitro-compound was precipitated in orange flocks which were collected and crystallised from dilute acetic acid in fine orange needles.

The substance is fairly soluble in most of the organic solvents and to a slight extent in water yielding intense yellow coloured solutions. On heating it does not melt, but at about 200° it gives off gas with explosive violence. When suddenly heated to a high temperature it explodes violently. Found: N, 9.5. $C_{13}H_{11}O_6(NO_2)_6$ requires N, 10.0 per cent.).

Oxidation of Hexanitro-hepta-acetyl-rottlerin with Potassium Permanganate.—The oxidation was carried out as in the case of hepta-acetyl-rottlerin (Dutt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, *loc. cit.*) by potassium permanganate in neutral solution. When the reaction was complete, the brown crystalline residue obtained after removal of the oxides of manganese, etc., by sulphur dioxide was filtered off and the mother-liquor also extracted several times with ether. The ether was distilled off and the residue added to the previous residue and the whole crystallised from dilute alcohol. A colourless crystalline acid was obtained, m.p. 179°, which was definitely identified to be 2:4-dinitro-benzoic acid.

The alcoholic mother-liquor, on evaporation to dryness, gave a colourless crystalline residue which, on repeated fractional crystallisation from water, was resolved into two acids melting at 200° and 278° respectively with decomposition. The former was identified to be 3:6-dinitro-phthalic acid while the latter was found to be 2:5-dinitro-terephthalic acid. Each of these two substances on dry distillation with soda-lime gave *p*-dinitro-benzene, m.p. 172°.

Hexabromo-hepta-acetyl-rottlerin, $C_{13}H_{11}O_6Br_6(C_6H_5O)_7$. Hepta-acetyl-rottlerin (10 g.), bromine (25 g.) and glacial acetic acid (20 c.c.) were heated in a sealed tube under pressure at 170° for about six hours. The product was isolated in the form of a brown amorphous powder. It could not be crystallised from any solvent since it is practically insoluble in everything. It does not melt on heating but undergoes decomposition above 300°.

(Found: Br, 35.2. $C_{11}H_7O_2Br_6$ (C_6H_5O), requires Br, 35.9 per cent.).

Hexabromo-rottlerin, $C_{11}H_7O_2Br_6$.—The above brom-acetyl compound (5g. was deacetylated by heating with concentrated hydrochloric acid (150 c.c.) under reflux for about six hours. The hexa-bromo-rottlerin was isolated as a dark brown powder, which could not be crystallised since it is practically insoluble in all the organic solvents. It does not melt on heating. Found: Br, 45.0. $C_{11}H_7O_2Br_6$ requires Br, 45.9 per cent.).

Oxidation of Hexabromo-hepta-acetyl-rottlerin with Potassium Permanganate.—The oxidation was carried out as in the previous instances and from the reaction product, 2:4-dibromo-benzoic acid, phthalic acid and terephthalic acid were isolated and identified.

Hexanitro-hexamethoxy-rottlerin, $C_{11}H_7O_9(NO_2)_6$.—Methoxy-rottlerin was nitrated by fuming nitric acid in the same manner as acetyl-rottlerin with formation of a hexa-nitro compound. It crystallises from acetic acid in orange brown glistening needles which decompose on heating. The substance is moderately soluble in most of the organic solvents. (Found: N, 8.61. $C_{11}H_7O_9(NO_2)_6$ requires N, 8.2 per cent.).

Oxidation of Hexanitro-hexamethoxy-rottlerin with Potassium Permanganate.—The oxidation was carried out as in the previous instances and from the product of the reaction three substances, namely 2:4-dinitro-benzoic acid, 3:6-dinitro-phthalic and 2:5-dinitro-terephthalic acid were definitely isolated and identified. No phloroglucinol derivative could be detected.

Further work in this direction is in progress.

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